

LANDLOCKED CENTRAL ASIA UP TO CONNECT WORLD'S BIGGEST PLAYERS

Azamkhujaev Umidkhon

PhD student at University of World Economy and Diplomacy (Tashkent, Uzbekistan); E-mail: umid.uzbek@gmail.com
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Transportation, which is critical in all economies, is doubly important for the economies of landlocked countries whose economic development is linked to the possibility of access to the sea. Since two-thirds of the earth's surface is water, transportation by sea is the most extensive, accessible and cheapest. For the world's 32 landlocked developing countries[1], coastal states are an invaluable link in the transport chain.

While international law traditionally recognizes the rights of every landlocked country to free access to the sea for expanding international trade and economic development[2], in practice, it's a different situation. Landlocked countries have to fight for the right to free access to the sea in order to participate in international trade. Leading international lawyers believe that the transit law of landlocked countries is not a principle recognized by international law, but rather a law governed by agreements concluded with coastal states[3].

All Central Asian countries, including Uzbekistan, are among the landlocked countries, and therefore face problems with access to global markets. In this regard, Uzbekistan has focused its foreign policy on the development of international transport corridors leading to seaports within the framework of regional economic integration.

The most ambitious is the Trans-Afghan Transport Corridor project, promoted by Uzbekistan in partnership with Pakistan and Afghanistan. The project was announced by the countries in 2021, and involves the construction of the Termez-Mazar-i-Sharif-Kabul-Peshawar railway, which will provide the closest and cheapest corridor connecting Pakistan to Central Asia, and Uzbekistan to the Pakistani ports of Karachi, Gwadar and Qasim.

Uzbekistan, also does not recognize the current Afghanistan as a full-fledged subject of international law like all countries of the world, however, demonstrating its commitment to following Article 55 of the UN Charter, Uzbekistan continues to cooperate with Afghanistan for the sake of stability, prosperity, economic and social development of the region, as well as in transport and transit. Uzbekistan draws the attention of the whole world to the

extreme importance of preventing the isolation of Afghanistan, and the need to integrate Afghanistan into interregional economic processes[4].

Another significant result is a trilateral agreement about the construction of the China-Kyrgyzstan-Uzbekistan railway signed in 2022, which is focused on construction of the missing part of Kyrgyz section of the road, that should connect the already existing railways in China and Uzbekistan.

The search for alternative transport routes bypassing Russia is prompting the European Union to work out routes through Central Asia. This idea is not new, the idea of connecting Europe and Central Asia with transport corridors originated in 1993, when the European Union established the program "Transport Corridor Europe-Asia-Caucasus (TRACECA)". The main goal was to create and develop a transport corridor from Europe through the Black Sea and further through the Caucasus and the Caspian Sea to Central Asia[5].

It is important to note that Central Asia has changed in recent years, becoming more open and showing serious efforts to integrate within the region, proclaiming this on the world stage[7]. The current Central Asia is aware that the geographical location of the countries of the region does not allow to implement large-scale projects along transport corridors on their own. Any route requires the assistance of several, and otherwise all, states of Central Asia. It's time to consider the unified transport network of Central Asia, laid out in the Soviet period as a single network with routes passing through the countries as a big benefit, contributing to regional integration.

In this light, attention should be paid to the efforts of Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan within the framework of the Organization of Turkic States (OTG). In 2022, in Samarkand (Uzbekistan), the Trade Facilitation Strategy of the OTG was approved by the member states, and the Agreement on the Formation of Simplified Customs Corridors was signed.

Teamed with Turkey, the sixths largest trading partner of the European Union[7], and also considering the existence of a functioning transport corridor "Baku - Tbilisi - Kars" with direct access to Europe, it can be confidently assumed that the OTG is the best platform for the countries of Central Asia to develop international transport corridors towards Europe.

If the European Union decides to participate in the project, this will fundamentally change all circumstances and encourage China, the second largest trading partner and largest importer for the European Union, to accelerate the construction of the railway and find the best solution of project funding. Undoubtedly, access to the European market via a shorter route through Central

Asia will not leave indifferent the ASEAN, the third largest trade partner of the European Union.

As for the countries of Central Asia, the prospect of access to global markets, the influx of considerable investments, the modernization and development of transport infrastructure, as well as the enormous replenishment of budgets from transit between the three largest economies of the world, will push to unite as a team, and maybe within the OTG. Maybe today's Central Asia understands that this is the most realistic chance to change the region's history

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